

Review on Security Challenges on Integrating WNS in Health care Services Networks with Internet of the things

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The present or review some existing literature on wireless sensor network challenges in health care services, also existing method of integrating Wireless sensor network in the internet of the things and propose frame work, their advantages and disadvantages.

Introduction

The dynamic changing in technology which brought things to object in an object oriented paradigm and smart object in an IoT paradigm. Things are interconnected together for easy accessibility, conveniences in use, and effective utilization, which had gives rise to a in matures domain refers to as internet of the thing. The IoT safe all objects to be interconnected together to share resource or exchange information such as hardware equipments, software and service provisions. The simulation and integrations of medical services in this field may yield many advantages towards effectives health care service delivery. This innovation had made people to access health care services at their door steps. Services such as urines test, blood test, body temperature measurement, hypotension test and many more tests at hospitals were carried out through connected machine terminals or sensors display in a strategic areas or in a non hospital premises . such as villages social

centre, homes, market places, schools, work places and many more places .Most of these automations and integrations of these machines in the domain of internet of thing had transformed physicians and patient way of discharging their duties and attending to a treatment of a particular diseases, and these suffering by both doctor and patient had came to its cured stage.

In conventional way, patients must transport themselves to a nearby hospitals before they can be treated. Also sometimes patient suffered before getting contact to the hospital premises which may leads too much suffering sometimes result to more deaths. To leaves safes with these catastrophes, is to provides connected machines terminals or sensors that will provide these services in most people s strategic and access full centers or integrate these services to be internet based service that will guarantees easy access to this service any where patients might be. Making medical services

sensors access full through cell phones chips will no doubt reduce suffering, increase more expertise in the field or sectors. Expectedly, the design of these machines or evolution of this domain may meet all the mentioned solutions to the problems above. Furthermore, smart devices such as patients monitoring system, blood pressure measuring device were invented to be integrated in the IOT paradigm to provide many services. Besides, technologies that detects and communicates patients data to either doctors or any processing unit which will examine patient information and yield result or set aside a treatment to the patient in respective of patient location. Many innovative systems were proposed in a modern medical healthcare approach to simplify doctors monitoring task at patient administered stage. Patient body temperature may communicate patient temperature reading to the doctors via smart bed system. To propose system that will

simulate conventional health care services and integrate in to the internet of the things, it might involve many paradigms such as cloud computing, wireless sensor network and e-health system web services.

Wireless sensor Network

According to (S. R. Vijayalakshmi* & S. Muruganand, 2016) Wireless Sensor Network is a network that has little or no infrastructure at all. It has fewer number of sensor nodes depending on its coverage area and this network can work together to monitor a region to obtain or sense data about the environment or some events such as patient information or body temperature. The network work and deployed based on its types, the structures have its nodes to be in an orderly deployed form while the unstructured wireless sensor nodes deployed in a random form in the intended location to capture data. The network is energy limited and specific application oriented meanwhile, despites of its energy

problems it can be deployed to provided specific application services such as health care services or environmental monitoring function.

Despite, different deployment form. Sensor networks inherit different characteristics, such as data flow pattern and energy constraints. In addition to data flow pattern, nodes in network sensor were deployed independent of each other to collect and send data to the central station. Sometimes work station will need specific data from a particular sensor nodes (S. R. Vijayalakshmi* & S. Muruganand, 2016). In such cases the work station will insert the query into the network and it is propagated. Then, the node with the NEEDED data will respond to the query with the relevant information and this information may be a captured data from a patient or senses from an environmental change. The major concern that will bring down the performance of the network was energy

constraints because the network operated with limited battery power as such it may operated within limited time unless another supporting measure were made. Since, uniquely wireless sensor network sensor could be specific application oriented networks that provides a specific services to a workstation as in (such case it insert the query into the network and it is propagated. then nodes with the data will responds to the query with the relevant information. In such case, it will insert the query into the network and it is propagated. Then nodes with the data will respond to the query with the relevant information as in (S. R. Vijayalakshmi*& S. Muruganand,2016). Then specific health care wireless network applications can be deployed TO provide medical services. The primary network performance metric of this network may be measured based on energy efficiency of operation (S. R. Vijayalakshmi* & S. Muruganand, 2016).

Integrating wireless sensor network and Internet of things

There are many approaches adopted to integrate a wireless sensor network into the internet of things to provide specific or general services to the user via internet protocols. A health care service specific wireless sensor network can be integrated with different deployed sensors to provide services to the users. Among, the approaches are front end, gateway and TCP/IP (S. R. Vijayalakshmi* & S. Muruganand, 2016).

The front end solution allow communication in between nodes internal to the network, the external internet hosts or nodes and the sensors nodes have no direct communication in between. Therefore, this network is completely independent of network. As such communication in these types of network may require implementation of its own set of protocols. Interactions between the outside world and the sensor network may be managed by a central device called base station as can be

seen bellow (S. R. Vijayalakshmi* & S. Muruganand, 2016).The base station stored information or data coming from the wireless sensors before sending to the internet or any external devices attached to the internet and then passed to the external entities (attached to the internet) through well known interfaces. In addition, any queries coming from Internet hosts shown bellow will always pass through the base station.

Figure 1.0 Front end approach for integrating WNS and IOT

As describes, the front end solution to integrating WSN and IoT requires sense information to moves through based station to any connected external entities. The gate-way approach, has an existence of a

device or nodes called base station that stand as an application layer protocol gateway, responsible for translating the lower layer protocols from both networks (e.g. TCP/IP and proprietary) and routing the information from one point to another as shown in fig bellow. As result of this connection Internet devices and sensor nodes can be able to address each other and exchange information without establishing a truly direct connection (S. R. Vijayalakshmi* & S. Muruganand ,2016). In this solution, the WSN is still independent from the Internet, as in its counterparts and all queries still need to transverse a gateway device. Also, sensor nodes can be able to provide web service interfaces to external entities (connected device) while maintaining their lower layer protocols.

Figure 2.0 Gate way approach for integrating WNS Network and IOT

The last or third approach used in integrating WSN Network and IOT ensures full -fledge implementation of internets, where sensor network nodes have direct connection to external hosts using TCP/IP protocol stack. Sensors network nodes exchanges health related information to any connected based-station using internet protocols. The drawback of this approach, in contrast to the other describes is that, the sensor network cannot implement specific WNS Protocols. The nodes in the WNS behaves in two (2) ways or have two (2) functions either front-end or Gate way. A WNS node as front end isolates the WNS nodes from communicating to any internet host and vice versa While, WNS nodes as

gate way allow direct exchange of information between WNS sensors with any connected based station. Also, according (Alok K, and S. Sathe,2014) classified the integration method based on how sensor nodes connect to the gateway devices. In the first approach which may be contrast to the method describes above, the sensor nodes connect to a single gateway devices and then connect to the internet, the approach describes as the most commonly used for WNS accessing the internet and present higher level of abstraction to the network. But the other two (2) approaches describes many sensor nodes node in the WNS connect to internets using a single gateway and the last approach combine the characteristic of the both approaches.

Indeed, often these difference approaches use for integrating WNS sensors and IOT, difference factors have to be considered for their choice. The factor are (RESILIENCE) security measures to ensures robustness of

their sensors nodes since the sensor nodes connect to the external system which had made them to be vulnerable to attacks. The security measures may be network parameter security devices such as honey-pots, intrusion Detection Systems and distributed system (Firewall) and encryption mechanism such as message hashing and data encryption.

Also, in the internet-based sensor nodes, they must implement user authentication and authorization mechanism, this security mechanism is to provide access control to users services access to the internet based sensor nodes applications.

Communication channels had to be secured to prevent data interception or tapping from eavesdroppers through TLS to offer end to end secure- channel and different key exchange mechanisms. Depending on the network integration or implementation the channels can be secured by providing one of the two (2) security measures approach,

either securing end to end communication in between connected host or securing the whole links. The transmitted information through the communication link from sensors to the processing unit of the machines has to be encrypted using asymmetric encryption algorithms. The decryption of these mechanisms is to have.....Also from security point of view, though costly, but developing WNS network with tamper resistant node as a countermeasure to prevent most of these health based WNS nodes that transmit captures data information from being intercepted and change (Yong Wang et. al, 2006).In another view, WNS node attack is un avoidable as such as IOT health care-based services may suffered from different attack right from the WNS node like attack against a routing protocol in any net-work these types of attack is to target the routing information while its being exchange between different node of the WNS or to

the connected based station, also secure socket layer(SSL) and Transport layer security (TLS) protocols are used to provide additional security to the mounted application in a HTML at transport layer.

Many counter measures approach to different attack i.e. Black hole, synbil, sinhole attack and e.t.c. That will compromise WNS node and result to altering or destruction of transmitted information belong to WNS were proposed some of these counter measures includes development of types of packet leases i.e. geographical and temporal leases incase of warmhole attack and e.t.c.

**Summary of Existing literatures on
Security challenges in four system
components**

Component	Security Challenges	Methodology	Author names
Wireless sensor network as e-health services and WNS Networks	Costly, reliability, legal, Legal issues, scalability, efficiency and data association problems, deployment	Front-end approach Gateway	

	environment, nodes in WNS have resource constraints, limited processing capability, storage capacity and communication bandwidth		
Cloud computing	Security and privacy issues, involvement		

	ent of third party		
	Data loss		
	Compro mise sensitive informati on, service interrupti ons, load balancing and standardi zation		
	Connecti on speed		
	Such as server response time.		
	Quality of service		
	Latency , packet		

	loss		
Web application	Privacy, system reliability and quality of service they provides, security lack of system truth worsness		JeongG il Ko1 Chenya ng Lu2 Mani B. Srivasta va3 John A. Stanko vic4 Andrea s Terzis1 Matt Welsh5
Integration of wireless sensor network with cloud	Key Distribut ion problem	Dynami c-proxy based approac h	By Swathi B S1, Dr. H S By

computing(method of intergration)	Mismatch in data format	Use of integration on controller unit Novel infrastructure	Guruprasad2 Sajjadat. Al By Vennila Santhanam 1
Internet of the things			
Integration of Wireless sensor in the cloud with internet of the things		Front-end and gateway	
Web services as	Lack of hardware independent		Vennila Santhanam 1, and Mr.

			D.B. Shanmugam
Internet of the thing			

There are many integration of cloud computing with Wireless sensor network despite the limitation of both domain such as security challenges and methodology in use i.e. packet loss, service interruption and lack of standardization to mentioned but few as presented in (J.SRINIVAS1 and K.VENKATA SUBBA, 2).Also J.SRINIVAS1 and K.VENKATA SUBBA, 2010) present wireless sensor integration frame work and the advantages of the integration is to move data from WNS to cloud environment for economically and scientific reasons, this moved data can be further utilized despites its drawback of latency, packet loss and service interruption.

Also another research work by (J.SRINIVAS1 and K.VENKATA SUBBA, 2) proposes wireless sensor network integration framework using proposed event matching algorithm. But the proposed frame work had minor flaw in its implementation publish/subscribes brokers. Another integration frame work was proposed by (J.SRINIVAS1 and K.VENKATA SUBBA, 2010) with grid computing, though it was inappropriate since cloud computing concentrate on general purpose application while grid is made mainly for large processing power, though the integration may requires large processing power but it may be out of focus. There are many applications of wireless sensor nodes such as rainfall and soil moisture monitoring and wind speed monitoring. In 2008-09 another implementation of largest land and water based sensor network, this node are meant to monitor drinking water in Australia by

CSIRO. If this innovative project continues, more sensor might be deployed to perform other task such as recording turbidity and temperature and send this data to their based station either traditional cell phone or remote data based. These may require extending the system by putting the data in to cloud and thereby permitting future research utilizing the data collected.

Conclusion

This present the review of the existing work in security and methodology challenges of integrating WNS network with IOT it shows two different methodologies used in integrating HEALTH care service sensor with IOT and a tables that summaries some challenges of various component. The overall system implementation will be better efficient if the underlined challenges are mitigated or solved or any one of the challenges, the work may be concentrating

to solve only one of the problems stated in
the survey.

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Expert approaches Fuzzy algorithms Fuzzy logics GPS and location-based applications Green Computing Grid Networking Healthcare Management Information Technology Human Computer Interaction (HCI) Image analysis and processing Image and multidimensional signal processing Image and Multimedia applications Industrial applications of neural networks Information and data security Information indexing and retrieval Information Management Information processing Information systems and applications Information Technology and their application Instrumentation electronics Intelligent Control System Intelligent sensors and actuators Internet applications and performances Internet Services and Applications Internet Technologies, Infrastructure, Services & Applications Interworking architecture and interoperability	Security, Privacy and Trust Security Systems and Technologies Sensor array and multi-channel processing Sensor fusion Sensors and RFID in pervasive systems Service oriented middleware Signal Control System Signal processing Smart devices and intelligent environments Smart home applications Social Networks and Online Communities Software Engineering Software engineering techniques for middleware Speech interface; Speech processing Supply Chain Management System security and security technologies Technology in Education Theoretical Computer Science Transportation information Trust, security and privacy issues in pervasive systems Ubiquitous and pervasive applications Ubiquitous Networks User interfaces and interaction models Virtual reality Vision-based applications Web Technologies Wired/Wireless Sensor Wireless technology
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